

A Critical Study of Imagery in John Keats “To Autumn”

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Abstract

Earning the appellation of a sensuous poet, John Keats emerged as one of the most revered Romantic poets. He has composed six odes in the year 1819 which are highly revered in British literature. “To Autumn” is an ode that has been accoladed for its use of rich imagery that savour the human mind. The paper attempts to study the imagery where Keats has played with sensuous elements, enriching the readers with the autumn season and its abundance. The paper shall also give a discourse on rhetorical techniques that aid in triggering the human senses to fully capture the essence of seasonal and old life experiences embedded in the ode. The ode seems to play with the images that constitutes the seasonal beauty yet it also foregrounds the underlying truth about human life via the help of imagination.

Keywords: imagery, sensuousness, imagination, romanticism

Introduction

John Keats was a versatile English Romantic poet who is widely recognized for his composition of odes. Keats was the last of the Romantics to compose poems and the first of the Romantics to die at a very young age of 25. His earlier poems were heavily criticized by Blackwood’s Edinburgh Magazine and The Quarterly Review for producing childish versification in his poems. Shelley, a contemporary poet of John Keats, wrote “Adonais” that strikes back at the Magazine and the Review while appreciating Keatsian imagination and his versification. His recognition aroused only after his decease and his odes and other poetical compositions are highly anthologised and evaluated in British Literature.

Keats wrote many letters which are now a part of Romantic criticisms to evaluate and appreciate the writings especially of Keats himself. He had given important statements on imagination and the idea of poetry. He also coined the term “negative capability” and “egotistical sublime” in his former letter to George and Thomas Keats on 21st December 1817 and the latter in his letter to Richard Woodhouse on 27th October 1818.

As a Romantic poet, Keats encapsulates the writing characteristics of negative capability, Hellenism, sensuousness, imagery, imagination, supernaturalism, beauty, nature and its solitary bliss as well as beauty, humanism and individualism. The ode “To Autumn” maps every Romantic trait celebrating the individual beauty of autumn season and the tapestry it unfolds through the imaginative and gentle flow of imagery resounding in the versification. Keats also

employs rhetorical devices such as caesura, personification, apostrophe, metaphor, simile rhetorical questions, alliteration, assonance and imagery.

The use of various rhetorical devices in the ode has a major implication in bringing forth the thematic structures and the creativity in the ode. It also enhances the beauty and odor of the poem via imagery that indicates the significance and the awe of the scenic autumnal season.

The nature is used widely to express the beauty of the seasons, birds, plants, animals or any other living organisms in Romantic poetry. Keats, however differ heavily from other Romantics as he uses the human senses by painting the images of natural world with the colourful words and verses with the aid of imagination that brings forth the fundamental aspect of human experiences. In Keatsian imagination, Keats describes that the objects perceived from the objective world when captured as beauty by the imaginative faculty also foregrounds the underlying truth about human experiences. Keats talks about it in his epistle to Benjamin Bailey on 22nd November, 1817 that “What the imagination seizes as Beauty must be truth” (Enright and Chickera, 256). This emphasizes the power of Keatsian imagination and it is reflected in all of his odes where the scenic imagery of nature also penetrates into the world of human life and their complex experiences.

The lyric “To Autumn” is divided into three stanzas and the imagery gives a vivid sensuous sensation to the mind of the readers. Many modern critics and scholars have noted the rich imagery in Keatsian odes where he plays with five human senses. The use of these senses helps the readers to generate a mental image and experience different dimensions of nature and of the truth about human experiences. Keats, as a Romantic poet is able to project the varieties of human experiences in his odes with the help of imagination.

The imagery in “To Autumn” is admired immensely for its rich tapestry of sensuousness. The human senses are deliberately placed to evoke an imaginative expression for readers to feel, taste, incense, hear and gaze at the abundance and rhythm of the season. The imagery “includes not only visual sense qualities but also qualities that are auditory, tactile (touch), thermal (heat and cold), olfactory (smell), gustatory (taste), and kinesthetic (sensations of movement)” (Abrams & Harpham, 172). These senses are embedded in the words that create images of different natural sceneries of the season.

Keats usage of images in the ode is an attempt to describe the “truth” of human life found in the seasonal beauty as caged by the imaginative mind of the poet. The vivid images also explore the Romantic element of humanism and individualism as well as negative capability. One can highlight that the imagery in “To Autumn” does not eliminate Romanticism but it offers the subjective nuances of the season while the negative capability depersonalizes the self of the poet creating an objective tone in the ode. “To Autumn” is a perfect exemplification that expresses the full maturity of Romanticism.

Methodology

The study uses a qualitative analysis by incorporating the close reading of the text. The text is read extensively and the various rhetorical devices, inputs or any technical analysis are used as

a tool to interpret the information and meaning to justify the implication it provides within the text.

The research paper is an attempt to examine the use of images and the various methods or ideas that has been employed by the poet to enrich the text are analysed using the critical concepts from Abrams and Harpham as well as Keat's various epistles that helps in illuminating the ideas behind the text. The other sources of information are also added as a secondary reference such as articles or other research papers to address the text.

Hypothesis

The ode "To Autumn" seems to deliberately use the imagery in a sensuous manner. The paper proposes the idea to explore the various sensuous elements in the ode and how it is structured and framed in the ode to give the impression to the readers. It also seems that the images in the ode also highlights the Romantic elements of humanism and individualism as well as negative capability which shall be tested based on the proximal reading of the text. The research assumes how imagination also plays a role in bringing forth the "truth" in "beauty" of the season.

Discussion

The ode opens with a thermal imagery and gustatory imagery of taste. It is a season of "mists" and "mellow fruitfulness" which represents the autumn's changing climate associated with transition between summer and winter, the latter is the plentiful of edible natural resources. These imageries project the autumn's seasonal climate and the it also provides a gustatory imagery projecting an impression of the varieties of fruits and vegetables that stimulate the palate of the readers. The gustatory imagery is heightened in the first stanza of the ode tempting the palate of the readers to enjoy the relish and the abundance that the season provides. The lines:

"To swell the gourd, and plump the hazel shells
With a sweet kernel; to set budding more,
And still more, later flowers for the bees,
Until they think warm days will never cease,
For summer has o'er-brimm'd their clammy cells".

The above lines are enriched with vivid gustatory images of taste indicative in the phrases such as "swell the gourd", "hazel shells", "sweet kernel", "clammy cells". These phrases are the stimulus of palate production that triggers the readers to enjoy and relish the seasonal abundance. These images are captivating suggesting that the season makes the vegetables such as "gourd" to have its pudge or the "hazel shells" along with its "kernel sweet" that has reached its full sweetness of taste. The phrase "clammy cells" is also indicative of vivid picture of honey in abundance agitating the palate organ of the readers to relish the seasonal abundance. Critically, the rhetorical elements of caesura and alliteration in the lines is specifically placed to put a stress and emphasis on the imagery. The phrases "swell to gourd" as well as "sweet kernel" have a caesura that functions in the ode to stimulate the sensual organ of gustatory in the form of imagery to the readers. It is intentionally placed to draw the attention of the readers

to enjoy the experience of the taste. The phrase “clammy cells” is an alliteration where the consonant sounds are repeated creating a musical rhythm. This musical rhythm not only praises the season but it also excites the gustation while the vivid images of palate play the mind of the readers. However, the lines reflect the beauty of the season yet it captures the underlying truth about human life and experiences. It is the imagination of the poet that skilfully encapsulates or correlate the season to the human experiences. These phrases evoke not only the gustatory images but it also foregrounds the life experiences of the old age. The infinitive verb “To swell” and the comparative adjective “more” along with the caesura heightens the wisdom of old age that comes with experiences. The lines “For summer has o’er-brimm’d their clammy cells” reflects how the wisdom in adulthood is overflowing or matured in the old age. It clearly proves Keatsian idea of imagination that captures the “truth” in the “beauty” of the season.

In addition to this, the visual imagery is another sensuous experience observed by the readers in the ode. This sense captures the vivid images that a human eyesight perceives and it is carefully crafted with the pictorial words or phrases. The visual images celebrate the beauty of the season as well as foregrounds the shadow of old age underneath with the help of imagination. The lines such as “To bend with apples the moss'd cottage-trees, /And fill all fruit with ripeness to the core;” gives a visual imagery in the ode celebrating the richness of autumn season. The lines suggest the plentiful of “apples” that has caused the tree itself to buckle due to its abundance. The imagination also captures the truth in the latter line where the phrases “ripeness to the core” symbolises the maturity of wisdom in old age. One can also observe the visual images in the lines such as “Sometimes whoever seeks abroad may find /Thee sitting careless on a granary floor” evinces the impression of sight that the seasonal beauty offers. The lines use an apostrophe “Thee” where the speaker is addressing to the season and the personification adds human qualities to the Autumn. The speaker is talking to the Autumn stating that the presence of Autumn is found by any as he sits idly “on a granary floor”. This visual image is evocative of the traits of season where people seem to take rest with less activities. It also brings forth the truth in the image about the old age experiences. It is a time where they spend less outside and they enjoy the bliss and solitude sitting inside their homes with less activity but a rest.

Furthermore, the visual imagery heightens the personification used in the ode. The personified figure Autumn is compared to a “gleaner” who after the reaper has harvested the fields, carries the remaining items in his back with a loaded “head across a brook”. These phrases give a visual sight creating an image in the mind of the readers of the reapers and gleaners who actually completes their harvesting journey. The simile that has been used in the visual imagery shows the theme of abundance the season provides and it also gives a human quality to Autumn season who himself is an abundance in the ode. However, the visual experiences also give a painting of Autumn’s colour. To quote:

“While barred clouds bloom the soft-dying day,
And touch the stubble-plains with rosy hue;”

The above lines throw shades into the picturesque painting of Autumn season. The alliterative phrases such as “barred clouds bloom” and “soft-dying day” gives a vivid visual impression in

the mind creating a beautiful setting of dying sun. The imagery is an expression of Autumn's individual beauty that separates itself from other seasons. The visual phrases states that the Autumn's setting sun is filled with the pinkish tinted glow spread all over the clouds while also reflecting on the "stubble-plains" creating a colour of "rosy hue". Critically, the words "soft-dying" and "stubble-plains" are hyphenated that draws attention to the beauty of Autumn season. The words emphasise the concrete visual images of the setting sun as well as the harvested fields while the "clouds" and "rosy hue" gives a colour to the season's landscape. The above lines celebrate the individual beauty of Autumn season creating a vivid visual imagery that provides calm and a meditative experience. Additionally, the imagery also combines the other sensuous element of tactile imagery. One can feel the sensation of sunlight that touches the "stubble-plains" with "rosy hue". The tactile image in the above line is combined along with a visual image to create a beautiful landscape of Autumn praising its unique qualities and its beauty.

Furthermore, the line such as "Thy hair soft-lifted by the winnowing wind" is also a good example of tactile imagery. Here, one can observe the sense of touch associated with the ability to feel the invisible. The tactile imagery triggers the reader to feel the gentle flow of wind that lifts the "hair" of Autumn at a glacial pace. The adjective "winnowing" gives two implications in the line suggestive of separating the chaff from grains or the light flow of wind. The tactile imagery can also indicate a metaphorical comparison between the separation of chaff from grains to the separation of Autumn's hair due to the gentle touch of wind. This clearly mark the important usage of images in the poem where the use of images "signifies figurative language, especially the vehicles of metaphors and similes" (Abrams & Harpham, 173).

Moreover, the olfactory imagery is another essential component used in the ode. The olfaction is one of the human senses that deals with the incense of the environment and its surroundings. The nasal and the olfactory nerve cells work as receptors that gives signal to the human mind to interpret the smell of the object. In the ode, the words and phrases use create a strong imagery of olfaction that helps the reader to imagine the incense of certain plants that emit scents and fragrances. To quote:

"Or on a half-reap'd furrow sound asleep,
Drowsed with the fume poppies, while thy hook
Spares the next swath and all its twined flowers:"

The given lines shows that Autumn can be found sleeping on the incomplete harvest fields under the influence of the incense "fume poppies". The phrase "fume poppies" marks the olfactory imagery in the ode highlighting the smell of the aromatic fragrance exhibited by the plant poppy. These plants have a therapeutic effect upon its scent that perhaps relaxes the mind leading to sleep inducing effect inside the nerve cells. The caesura also functions in the line next to "fume poppies" indicating its emphasis on olfaction to the readers to submerge into the effects of the poppy plant. As the olfaction has a drowsiness effect on Autumn, he lays down his "hook" to rest and he leaves the other "twined flowers" from being cut while enjoying the incense of the poppy. As the lines capture the "beauty" of Autumn season, it also brings forth the underlying "truth" of human experiences. The imaginative faculty transform the beauty to

highlight the fact about the old age experiences. The lines also reflect the rest and inaction of old age who prefers sleeping or resting during this phase. “To Autumn” is an ode that encapsulates this mark of old age phase in the images while reducing the activity of daily life and struggles.

The olfactory image also teases the smell of the readers with liquor and intoxicant extract of drinks from natural fruit. The phrase is powerful enough to evoke the impression on the readers to relish the incense of the drink as well as ponder about the seasonal blessings. To quote:

“Or by a cyder-press, with patient look,
Thou watchest the last oozings hours by hours.”

The above lines are a clear indication of Autumn who patiently looks after the alcoholic liquor being made from the machine “oozings hours by hours”. The lines also reflect the theme of abundance of Autumn especially the extraction of wines from the natural fruit. The “cyder-press” uses both hyphen and a caesura that functions to set the impression on the olfaction of the readers. The word is powerful enough along with the caesura that pauses for the readers to relish the seasonal blessing it has to offer. However, the lines also combine the visual imagery to perceive the image to the readers of what Autumn perceives the “last oozings” of the apple beverage. The visual image in the line act as a medium of sight for the readers to gaze at the “cyder-press” for it is Autumn who allows the readers to visualise into it.

Moreover, the third stanza of the ode shows the musical flow of Autumn season and it triggers the auditory sense of the readers. The hearing sense is evident in the singing of the varieties of birds as well as the pastoral animal that brings comfort and joy to the readers. To quote:

“Then in a wailful choir the small gnats mourn
Among the river shallows, borne aloft
Or sinking as the light wind lives or dies:
And full-grown lambs loud bleat from hilly bourn;
Hedge-crickets sing; and now with treble soft
The red-breast whistles from a garden-croft;
And gathering swallows twitter in the skies.”

The given lines are a clear exemplification of an auditory imagery. The lines use the onomatopoeia technique such as “mourn”, “bleat”, “sing”, “treble”, “whistles” and “twitter” which trigger the hearing sense to enjoy its bliss in the mind of the readers. The lines suggest that one could observe the sorrowful sound of the “small gnats” coming from the willow trees that “lives or dies” depending on the flow of wind. The adult pastoral animal such as the lamb also make a sound bleating from “hilly bourn” that soothes the listener. The depiction of varieties of birds also shows the abundance of Autumn not only of its flora species but also of the fauna species. The “Hedge-crickets” beautifully creates a musical tone for Autumn as well as the “red-breast” starts whistling from the garden. The “swallows” gather around in the sky twittering giving a musical expression for Autumn season. The image ranges from “Hedge-crickets”, “red-breast” and “swallows” which are different species of birds that chirps during the season. The auditory sense of the readers get trigger to hear the sound of these birds to enjoy the calming effect it has on the readers and the environment. Critically, the caesura is

used near the word “sallows” and “sing” to give the impression of the natural world as well as to trigger the hearing sense of the reader. The fauna and flora species also uses hyphenated words such as “full-grown lambs”, “Hedge-crickets” and “red-breast” which also gives an impression on the readers to ponder about the different varieties of birds and their chirping sounds. The use of hyphen also helps to enrich the stanza with different types of birds as well as an animal that celebrates the beauty of Autumn season.

The imagery in the ode also remarkably gives a picturesque colour of Romanticism. Keats, as a Romantic poet did not follow the philosophical flights of imagination like Wordsworth or penetrates into the realm of mystery like Coleridge. He uses images that captures the essence of Romanticism highlighting the full maturity of Romantic age in his ode. The Romantic age focuses on the world of nature and rural landscape, evident in the “To Autumn”. The ode is not only a celebration of Autumn season but also of the beauty of nature as well as the rural lifestyle. Autumn is personified to a farmer and the “gleaner” in the ode giving him a quality of a person set in the rural scenario. The Romantics also depict the pastoral animals and other fauna species in their writings. “To Autumn” also presents an image of a “full-grown lambs” bleating as well as “Hedge-crickets”, “red-breast” and “swallows” singing or twittering either from the garden or the sky. These depictions are embedded in the form of an image in the ode where the romantic elements are weaved along with the human sense to fully relish the experience.

However, the ode also presents the romantic elements of humanism as well as individualism through imagery. In the context of humanism, the ode uses images that gives the visual sight of setting of the sun. For instance, the imagery of “maturing sun” as well as “soft-dying day” paints a picture of Autumn colour. It represents the ephemeral state of day transitioning into darkness which are the keen exploration in humanism. Additionally, the theme of humanism can be seen in the writing style of ode. As humanism focuses on classical learning, the ode imitates Horatian ode and its characteristics. The typical traits of “Horatian odes are calm, meditative and colloquial” (Abrams & Harpham, 263). The use of apostrophe gives a colloquial undertone in the poem where there is a speaker addressing to the autumn season. The rhetorical questions such as “Who hath not seen thee oft amid thy store?” has a colloquial conversational undertone where the speaker is addressing to Autumn. The apostrophe such as “thee” and “thy” bridges communication and it underscores the existence of the listener and the speaker. The other lines also use apostrophe such as “thou” which also reflects the use of colloquialism in the ode reflecting the traits of Horatian ode.

The Horatian ode is also noted for its calm and meditative use of language or phrases in the writing. The imagery in the lyrical poem uses an adjective such as “winnowing wind”, “soft-lifted”, “soft-dying day”, “light wind” and “treble soft” adds a calm and meditative mood to the ode. In contrast to Wordsworth’s meditative musings in the mind, the ode “To Autumn” is able to evoke the meditative and calm translation of feelings and emotions through the imagery and the various sensory experiences. The given notable phrases in the ode showcases the gentle flow of nature as well as the calm mediation mood of the setting sun which adds a beautiful replica to Horatian ode.

Furthermore, the imagery not only reflect humanism and classical imitation of Horatian ode but also of individualism and negative capability which are the other essential qualities of Romanticism. Romanticism as a movement makes a person different and unique from others. The Romantics celebrate individuality in their poems. In “To Autumn”, the individualism is the celebration of Autumn. Since Autumn is a personified figure in the ode, the individual nature of the season and its beauty is celebrated. To quote:

“Where are the songs of Spring? Ay, Where are they?
Think not of them, thou has thy music too,”

The above line is a clear exemplification of Romantic individualism. The line celebrates the individuality and its unique qualities of Autumn season. The rhetorical question and an apostrophe add a colloquial undertone reflecting the traits of Horatian ode. The speaker asks Autumn about the whereabouts of “Spring” and its music. However, the speaker tells Autumn not to imagine about “Spring” for Autumn has its own “music” too which reflects the celebration of Autumn’s individual quality. The image in the lines also capture a sense of negative capability where the speaker leads Autumn to a state of uncertainty about the whereabouts of “Spring” season but Autumn lives with this state of uncertainty in the present state without any logical conclusion while enjoying its own “music” and beauty to appreciate. This clearly projects the use of negative capability in the ode. It is also evident when Autumn, under the influence of “poppies” rests his “hook” while sparing the flowers that needed to be cut suggest the ability of Autumn to enjoy the present state of moment while subtracting any plausible explanations as to his need for rest and relish the aromatic scent of “poppies”. It can also be noted that negative capability in Keats ode also subtracts the shadow of the poet himself making the ode objective and impersonal. One can assess the ode “To Autumn” that it is not a subjective experience of the poet but of a personified figure Autumn. The use of apostrophe and personification clearly marks the depersonalisation of poet who maintains his distance from opining any personal or subjective views in the ode. Hence, the ode is an objective experience of Autumn season where the shadow of Keats himself is subtracted and the readers are able to immerse into the world of Autumn without the weight of poet’s personal beliefs or knowledge.

Therefore, in conclusion, the ode “To Autumn” is a beautiful expression of the season’s beauty and its celebration of individuality. The use of imagery is rich with sensuousness that triggers the human senses to relish the delicacy of the season. The images also capture the Romantic aura and it does not diminish the Romanticism. Keats is able to fully encapsulate the world of Romanticism in an objective manner with the use of images and negative capability that makes the poet to distant away his self from his aesthetics. Hence, one can rightly state that “To Autumn” is a perfect example of the full maturity of Romanticism where he is able to express the Romantic essence of calm, meditative, pastoral and rural simplicity objectively with the use of imagery.

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